

Radiation effect of M-slot patch antenna for wireless application

Yousif Allbadi¹, Huda Ibrahim Hamd², Ilham H. Qaddoori¹

¹Department of Communication, Collage of Engineering, University of Diyala, Ba'qubah, Iraq

²Department of Electronics, Collage of Engineering, University of Diyala, Ba'qubah, Iraq

Article Info

Article history:

Received Mar 13, 2022

Revised Apr 11, 2022

Accepted Jul 4, 2022

Keywords:

M-slot

Patch antenna

Specific absorption rate

Wi-Fi

Wi-Max

ABSTRACT

Today, the specific absorption rate has become an important and necessary measurement when designing and implementing any type of antenna. In recent years, various devices have appeared that use different frequencies for wireless communication systems, which are a source of electromagnetic radiation. The M-slot antenna is designed in this paper to operate in multi-band frequencies for wireless communications using computer simulation technology (CST) software 2020. The radiation effect for this antenna is calculated for tissue mass of the human fingertips, which consists of three layers (skin, meat, and bone), over a mass of 1 g and 10 g according to the IEEE and International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) organization. The results are shown three applications in the communication system, which are Wi-Fi, worldwide interoperability for microwave access (Wi-Max) and, satellite X-band and, the value of specific absorption rate (SAR) increase with increased frequency.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Yousif Allbadi

Department of Communication's, College of Engineering, Diyala University

Ba'qubah 32002, Diyala, Iraq

Email: yousifallbadi@uodiyala.edu.iq

1. INTRODUCTION

As the effect of the huge evolution in the wireless broadband communication besides the emergence of different types of devices that use antennas radiating electromagnetic waves, anxiety has increased among humans because of the radiation emitted from these devices and the health implications of that [1]-[10]. International organizations such as the World Health Organization and the Federal Communications Commission have developed regulatory guidelines for electromagnetic energy around the world to protect against non-ionizing radiation emitted from these devices. In addition, there is a group of countries that have set their own guidelines for the permissible amount of electromagnetic energy. All of these tributes are designed to protect humans and living things such as plants and flowers from the effects of radiation [11]-[15]. There are a lot of institutes that have developed a standard for measuring the electromagnetic energy radiate absorbed by human tissue, known as the specific absorption rate (SAR) such as International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP) and IEEE. SAR can be calculated for all human body or for part of it and (1) is represented this [16]-[20].

$$SAR = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{dw}{\rho dm} \right) \quad (1)$$

where, dw=absorbing energy

dm=change in mass

ρ =density

According to (1), the unit of SAR is (W/Kg) or (mm/g). In addition, SAR can be calculated as an electric field and can be seen in (2).

$$SAR = \sigma E^2 / \rho \quad (2)$$

where σ =conductivity for biological tissue in (S/m)

ρ =density for biological tissue in (Kg/m³)

The ICNIRP and the IEEE has determined the amount of electromagnetic radiation that an organism is allowed to absorb without any negative impact on it. The specific absorbing rate is set at 2 watt/kilogram and 1.6 watt/kilogram for 10 gram and 1 gram of human tissues according to IEEE and ICNIRP respectively. There are many studies have been focused on the topic, two types of antennas are designed and compared, one is a dipole and the other is a square patch antenna. The SAR rate for both is calculated for human head tissue placed at a distance of 5 cm [2]. The square microstrip antenna is designed at 2.4 GHz and the radiation effect of the human head is simulated at distance of 5 cm. Different sizes are taken from the human head (child, young, and adult) [3].

The absorption rate of the fingers of an adult human being is calculated through the radiation sent from a Fractal Sierpinski Square patch antenna at 1.575 GHz [4]. While in [7] SAR is calculated for head tissues placed near fractal sausage minkowski at 1.575 GHz also. The absorption rate of the cylindrical patch antenna with a frequency 6.7 GHz of the human head is calculated according to ICNIRP [8].

In this paper, the specific absorbing rate for fingers tissues, which are consist of skin, meat, and bone, is calculated for the M-slot patch antenna. The proposed antenna is operated at multiband frequencies.

2. ANTENNA DESIGN

In the last two decades and the tremendous development in wireless communications, essentially in applications of antenna that need a frequency of 1-10 GHz, like Wi-Fi, worldwide interoperability for microwave access (Wi-Max), and global positioning system (GPS). The patch antenna is one of the famous types of antenna that is used because of having particular specifications in terms of size and weight [21]-[25]. The patch antenna consists of three main layers, ground, dielectric, and patch layers. In order to design the antenna with better efficiency and greater bandwidth, the length of the radiating layer should be less than half the wavelength, and the dielectric layer should be thick and with a relatively low isolation coefficient [26]-[29]. In this paper, the thickness of two radiate layers (patch & ground) is ($t=0.035$) mm, made of copper material, while the thickness of dielectric layer (substrate) is ($h=1.5$) mm, made of FR-4 epoxy material which is the relative permittivity of 4.3. Figures 1(a) to (b) and Table 1 are shown propose antenna dimensions with 50 Ω matching impedance [30].

Figure 1 M-slot antenna (a) front view and (b) back view

Table 1. Proposed antenna dimensions

Parameters	Values (mm)
LG	60
lg	38
w1	2
w2	4
w3	3
w4	10
w5	32
wf	3.7
lf	11

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

M-slot antenna is simulated, designed using computer simulation technology (CST) software 2020. Table 2 records all the characteristics of proposed antenna [30]. Figure 2 shows, the reflection coefficient for M-slot patch antenna. In addition, there are 6 bands of operating frequency ($f_1=2.4$, $f_2=4.55$, $f_3=7.8$, $f_4=8.3$, $f_5=9$, and $f_6=9.9$) GHz. notice it is operated at multi band wireless application.

Table 2. Specific parameters of antenna

Specifics	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
RC dB	-32	-21	-28	-15	-16_-14	-31
Gain dBi	4.97	5.95	9.24	5.56	8.15	7.23
Directivity dBi	6.35	6.44	9.78	6.1	8.5	7.62
SWR	1.01	1.18	1.07	1.2	1.4	1.06
BW MHz	55	85	78	71	510	170
Zo	50	48.99	49	48	48	50

Figure 2. Reflection coefficient of antenna

From the Table 2, it can be seen that the characteristic parameters of proposed antenna recorded good values for all the frequencies. In this paper, the SAR values for the hand tissues are simulated using CST 2020 software. The SAR calculation is obtained for ICNIRP and IEEE world standard. The hand tissues consist of three layers: skin, meat, and bone. The SAR values is recorded for four band frequencies: 2.4, 4.55, 7.8, and 8.3 GHz.

Figures 3(a) and (b), Figures 4(a) and (b), Figures 5(a) and (b), Figures 6(a) and (b), show the SAR levels for two standards ICNIRP and IEEE. It is observed that the values of SAR at 10 g are smaller than 1 g, this is due to the increased mass of tissues exposed to radiation. In addition, the level of SAR values is directly proportional to the frequency for both standards.

From Table 3, it appears the results of radiation levels at 10 g and 1 g for 4 band frequencies. At 1 g recorded (0.242, 0.52, 0.553, and 0.785) w/kg and 10 g (0.174, 0.369, 0.391, and 0.558) w/kg. All SAR values are recorded within acceptable levels with low radiation ratios for both standards and all frequencies.

Figure 3. Radiation effect of the antenna at f1 (a) 1 gram and (b) 10 grams

Figure 4. Radiation effect of the antenna at f2 (a) 1 gram and (b) 10 grams

Figure 5. Radiation effect of the antenna at f3 (a) 1 gram and (b) 10 grams

Figure 6. Radiation effect of the antenna at f4 (a) 1 gram and (b) 10 grams

Table 3. SAR levels for proposed antenna

SAR level	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4
1 g	0.242	0.52	0.553	0.785
10 g	0.174	0.369	0.391	0.553

4. CONCLUSION

In recent years, there has been a strong demand in the global market to design a single antenna operating at multi bands frequencies in wireless communication applications. In this paper, M-slot antenna is measured and designed for main 4 band frequencies, 2.4, 4.5, 7.8, and 8.3 GHz. In addition, SAR is calculated over figure tissues according to IEEE and ICNIPR standards. The values of SAR for IEEE standard is smaller than ICNIPR standard.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Sabah and M. J. Frhan, "A new patch antenna for ultra-wide band communication applications," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 18, no. 2, May 2019, pp. 848-855, 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v18.i2.pp848-855.
- [2] I. H. Ali, H. I. Hamd and A. I. Abdalla, "Design and comparison of two types of antennas for SAR calculation in wireless applications," *2018 Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences (ASET)*, 2018, pp. 1-5, doi: 10.1109/ICASET.2018.8376891.
- [3] A. M. Ahmed, "Specific absorption rate (SAR) simulated for square patch antenna of head tissues," *Engineering and Technology Journal*, vol. 36, no. 5, 2018, doi: 10.30684/etj.36.5A.5.
- [4] K. H. Kuther, I. H. Ali, and R. K. Ahmed, "Radiation effect of fractal sierpinski square patch antenna," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5329-5334, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v10i5.pp5329-5334.
- [5] L. El Amrani, T. Mazri, and N. Hmina, "Propagation models approach for the study of human specific absorption rate," *2019 11th International Conference on Electronics, Computers and Artificial Intelligence (ECAI)*, 2019, pp. 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ECAI46879.2019.9041971.
- [6] R. H. Mahdi and H. A. Jawad, "Assessment of specific absorption rate and temperature in the tumor tissue subjected to plasmonic bow-tie optical nano-antenna," *2019 International Engineering Conference (IEC)*, 2019, pp. 28-33, doi: 10.1109/IEC47844.2019.8950609.
- [7] R. K. Ahmed and I. H. Ali, "SAR level reduction based on fractal sausage minkowski square patch antenna," *Journal of Communications*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 82-87, Jan. 2019
- [8] K. Jayabharathy and S. Ilakkia, "SAR Analysis of microstrip patch antenna in human head," *2020 7th International Conference on Smart Structures and Systems (ICSSS)*, 2020, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ICSSS49621.2020.9202240.
- [9] F. Fereidouni, S. T. Mohammadi, V. F. Shahraki, and F. Jahantigh, "Human health risk assessment of 4-12 Ghz radar waves using CST studio suite software," *Journal of Biomedical Physics and Engineering. Original Research*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 285-296, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.31661/jbpe.v0i0.1272.
- [10] D. Mitra, S. Das, and S. Paul, "SAR reduction for an implantable antenna using ferrite superstrate," *2019 International Workshop on Antenna Technology (iWAT)*, 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/IWAT.2019.8730853.
- [11] V. Stanković, V. Marković, D. Jovanović, D. Krstić, and N. Cvetković, "Distribution of the absorbed mobile phone energy at 1.8 and 2.1 GHz in a child head model," *IEEE EUROCON 2019-18th International Conference on Smart Technologies*, 2019, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/EUROCON.2019.8861511.
- [12] A. D. Farhood, M. K. Naji, S. H. R. H. Rhaif, and A. Ali, "Design and analysis of dual band integrated hexagonal shaped microstrip UWB antenna," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 861-869, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v15.i1.pp294-299.
- [13] I. H. Ali and R. K. Ahmed, "The Performance evaluation of SAR for a Sausage minkowski square patch antenna," *Al-Nahrain Journal for Engineering Sciences (NJES)*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 208-212, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.29194/NJES21020208.
- [14] M. A. A. Aziz, N. Seman, and T. H. Chua, "Microstrip antenna design with partial ground at frequencies above 20 GHz for 5G telecommunication systems," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1466-1473, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v15.i3.pp1466-1473.
- [15] I. H. Ali and R. K. Ahmed, "The effects evaluation of various dielectric substrate of square patch antenna on SAR Level for human head," *Journal of engineering and applied sciences*, vol. 13, no. 9, pp. 2761-2766, 2018.
- [16] M. T. Islam, M. R. I. Faruque, and N. Misran, "Reduction of specific absorption rate (SAR) in the human head with ferrite material and meta material," *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*, vol. 9, pp. 47-58, 2009, doi: 10.2528/PIERC09062303.
- [17] T. Khalifa, N. M. Sahar, N. Ramli, and M. T. Islam, "Circularly polarized microstrip patch antenna array for GPS application," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 920-926, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v15.i2.pp920-926.
- [18] R. L. Waechter and L. Sergio, "Manipulation of the electromagnetic spectrum via fields projected from human hands: a qi energy connection?," *Subtle Energies & Energy Medicine Journal Archives*, vol. 13, no. 3, 2002.
- [19] C. Li, M. Douglas, E. Ofli, N. Chavannes, Q. Balzano, and N. Kuster, "Mechanisms of RF electromagnetic field absorption in human hands and fingers," in *IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques*, vol. 60, no. 7, pp. 2267-2276, July 2012, doi: 10.1109/TMTT.2012.2197019.
- [20] A. Othman, N. I. S. Shaari, A. M. Zobilah, N. A. Shairi, and Z. Zakaria, "Design of compact ultra-wideband antenna for microwave medical imaging application," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1197-1202, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v15.i3.pp1197-1202.
- [21] M. Vuchkovikj, I. Munteanu, and T. Weiland, "Application of postured human model for SAR measurements" *Advances in Radio Science*, vol. 11, pp. 347-352, 2013, doi: 10.5194/ars-11-347-2013.
- [22] C. J. Panagamuwa, I. Howells and A. Kotb, "Use of a block hand phantom for mobile phone Specific Absorption Rate measurements," *2013 7th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, 2013, pp. 911-914.
- [23] S. M. Ali, V. Jeoti, T. Saedi, and W. P. Wen, "Design of compact microstrip patch antenna for WBAN applications at ISM 2.4 GHz," *Indonesian Journal of Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (IJECS)*, vol. 15, no. 3, pp. 1509-1516, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijeecs.v15.i3.pp1509-1516.
- [24] A. El Hamdouni, A. Tajmouati, J. Zbito, A. Tribak, and M. Latrach, "Novel fractal antenna for UWB applications using the coplanar waveguide feed line," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 3115-3120, Aug. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i4.pp3115-3120.
- [25] Y. Rahayu and R. A. Gusma, "Simulation of 6 elements aperture coupled feed planar array rectangular microstrip patch antenna for CPE WiMAX application at 3.3 GHz," *Proceeding of International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Computer Science and Informatics (EECSI 2014)*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 451-455, Aug. 2014, doi: 10.11591/eeesi.v1.384.
- [26] A. Zaidi, A. Baghdad, A. Ballouk, and A. Badri, "Design and optimization of a high gain multiband patch antenna for millimeter wave applications," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 8, no. 5, pp. 2942-2950, Oct. 2018, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v8i5.pp2942-2950.
- [27] M. ElJourmi, H. Ouahmane, and F. Kharroubi, "Design and simulation of UWB microstrip patch antenna for Ku/K bands applications," *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 4845-4849, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v9i6.pp4845-4849.
- [28] R. K. Ahmed and I. H. Ali, "Toward an optimum design of fractal sausage Minkowski antenna for GPS applications," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 1, February 2022, pp. 293-298, DOI: 10.11591/eei.v11i1.3333.

- [29] I. H. Ali and R. K. Ahmed, "Fractal Sierpinski square patch antenna for GPS applications," *2nd International Conference on Sustainable Engineering Techniques (ICSET 2019), IOP Conf. Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, vol. 518, no. 4, p. 042007, 2019.
- [30] A. I. Abdalla and I. H. Ali, "Design and modification of multiband M-slot patch antenna for wireless applications," *2020 IEEE 17th International Conference on Smart Communities: Improving Quality of Life Using ICT, IoT and AI (HONET)*, 2020, pp. 99-102, doi: 10.1109/HONET50430.2020.9322656.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Yousif Allbadi received master's degree in Telecommunications Engineering from the Warsaw University of Technology, Poland. He is working as a lecturer in the Department of Communications Engineering/the University of Diyala. The field of scientific research is focused on embedded systems, IoT, modern communications, and deep learning. He can be contacted at email: yousifallbadi@uodiyala.edu.iq.

Huda Ibrahim Hamd is a lecturer at the Department of Electronic Engineering, University of Diyala, Iraq, since 2013. Huda graduated B.Eng. degree in Communication Engineering from Diyala University, Iraq, in 2007, and a M.Sc. in Electronic and communication Engineering from Almustansiriya University, Iraq in 2013. Her research interests are in the area of wireless communications especially in biomedical engineering and antenna design. She can be contacted at email: ihhhuda@yahoo.com.

Ilham H. Qaddoori is a lecturer at the Department of Communication Engineering, University of Diyala, Iraq, since 2021. She graduated B.Eng. degree in Electronic and Communication Engineering from Baghdad University, Iraq, in 1993, and a M.Sc. in Electronic and communication Engineering from Almustansiriya University, Iraq in 2021. Her research interests are in antenna design and microwave system. She can be contacted at email: eema1035@uomustansiriyah.edu.iq.